

An Analysis Of The Black-Scholes Model For Option Pricing

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Abstract

An option is a contract between two parties with opposing views on an underlying asset. The option's premium is what the writer (seller) decides the buyer must pay per share of the option. The Black-Scholes model is a mathematical model that uses stochastic processes, geometric Brownian motion, and other assumptions to price options. This paper aims to understand how the Black-Scholes model works along with when it is an appropriate method for pricing options. In general, the model is considered accurate, although during periods of extreme events, rapid price movements, and high volatility, the model fails to price options accurately. Hence, when pricing options, the Black-Scholes Model would not be an appropriate choice for times of extreme events or high volatility. Otherwise, the model is considered accurate and can be a great tool for pricing options efficiently.

Introduction to Options

The term options refers to a financial instrument dictated by an underlying asset's value. Options are a form of financial derivative in which two parties agree to transact an asset at a specified price or date. An option that bets that the underlying asset's price will go up is called a call option; betting that it will go down is called a put option. An option has a strike price and a premium. The strike price is the agreed-upon price of the asset when the option is written. The premium is the money that the buyer of the contract has to pay the writer for convenience. The price at which the option is exercised is called the exercise price. A European call option is an option contract that limits its execution to an exercise date. An American option can be exercised at any time (including the expiration date).

Importance of the Black-Scholes Model

As the premium of an option can dictate how much money each party can get (if at all), it is vital to price the premium correctly. This is to balance the risk and reward so that one ends up with an option that is not only beneficial to them but also enticing enough so that someone buys it. The Black-Scholes Model is extremely important in the financial industry due to its ability to take in mathematical parameters and price options. Without it, firms and sellers

would have to use trial-and-error and the process could be very tedious and costly. The intention for this deep dive into the Black-Scholes Model is not only to gain a deeper understanding as to why it works but also to understand when it does and does not work. Through this, one can understand when to use the model to maximize profits from option transactions.

Assumptions of the Black-Scholes Model

There are a few assumptions made by the Black-Scholes model for it to work. Some of these assumptions can question the accuracy of the model. One of these is that the option does not pay dividends. Factoring dividends into the model would be too complicated as it is not uniform, and so the model assumes that no dividends or distributions are paid. Another assumption is that markets are random and cannot be predicted. It also assumes that the risk-free rate and the volatility of the asset are known in advance and constant throughout the life of the option. For the model to work the returns of the underlying asset are normally distributed. Most importantly, this model only works for European options that are only exercised at the expiration date.

Some of these assumptions are more valid than others. The underlying assets are normally distributed, and the option does not pay dividends, the volatility is constant are examples of assumptions that can limit the accuracy of the model as they do not hold for the real world. For example, the normal distribution assumption can be quite problematic as riskier assets would be more skewed. For instance, equity returns across different timelines are typically negatively skewed and have fat tails (big downside moves are more common than big upside moves). This could lead to an underpricing or overpricing of some assets. Similarly, the no dividend assumption could lead to limitations, especially for options with dividends. Equity options have the greatest possibility for dividends, which the model does not factor in. Additionally, for the volatility assumption, the volatility is neither constant nor known in advance. As volatility is an input in the model it has to be constant, but in reality this does not happen. Some assumptions such as the market being random and the fact that it only works for European options are not that massive. As far as we can comprehend, the market is random, and even when it is predicted the prediction's accuracy is random. Plus, for American options, there are too many constantly changing variables to be computed, and half the options written are European so it does not pose too much of an issue.

Stochastic Process and Geometric Brownian Motion

The stochastic process refers to an infinite collection of random variables that are indexed by some mathematical set. They are widely used as mathematical models of systems or phenomena that appear to vary randomly. It describes the evolution of a system over time in a probabilistic manner. The random variables represent the state of the system at different points in time. A stochastic process is defined as a family of random variables, $\{X(t): t \in T\}$. T is typically a set representing time, and each random variable $X(t)$ represents the system at a particular time (t). The set T can be discrete or continuous. Each random variable $X(t)$ has its probability distribution. The joint distribution of multiple variables can be considered to analyze their relationships. There are multiple stochastic processes, including discrete-time and continuous-time processes. Discrete-time processes are defined at specific time points, such as a sequence of random variables $\{X_1, X_2, X_3 \dots\}$. On the other hand, continuous-time processes are defined over a continuous range of time, such as the function $X(t)$.

Brownian motion is a continuous stochastic process that describes random movement. It is a term used in physics to describe the random movement of particles. Brownian motion has three key characteristics:

1. Randomness: Brownian motion is an example of a stochastic process, and an example is the position of a particle and how it changes randomly over time. The direction and the magnitude of each displacement of the particle are dictated by random forces acting on the particle.

2. Markov Property: Markov property states that the future behavior of a Brownian motion process depends on its current state and is independent of its past states. It essentially states that the motion has no memory.

3. Diffusion: Diffusion (not only in the scientific way), is an important part of Brownian motion. It states that the effect of the Brownian motion spreads and thus affects a larger area.

All of these characteristics make Brownian motion an example of a continuous-time stochastic process.

Geometric Brownian motion (GBM) is a stochastic process that is used to model the dynamics of asset prices (stocks or commodities), where the logarithmic returns follow a Brownian motion. It is an extension of Brownian motion that incorporates a drift term and accounts for exponential growth or decay. The GBM process is defined by a stochastic differential equation.

$$dS(t) = \mu S(t)dt + \sigma S(t)dW(t)$$

$S(t)$ represents the asset price at time t .

μ is the average rate of return (drift) of the asset.

σ is the volatility of the asset's returns.

$dW(t)$ represents the differential of a standard Brownian motion, which accounts for the random component of the process.

The log-normal distribution is a key property of GBM. By taking the natural logarithm (base e) of both sides of the GBM, you get the equation:

$$d(\ln(S(t))) = (\mu - 0.5 \sigma^2)dt + \sigma dW(t)$$

The term $(\mu - 0.5 \sigma^2)dt$ represents the drift, and the term $\sigma dW(t)$ represents the diffusion. Hence, the log returns have a normal distribution with a mean of $(\mu - 0.5 \sigma^2)dt$ and a standard deviation of $\sigma \sqrt{dt}$. GBM allows for exponential growth or decay in asset prices. The term $\mu S(t)dt$ in the equation refers to the expected return rate, causing the asset price to shrink or grow exponentially over time. It also exhibits a scaling property similar to that of Brownian motion. If the time interval by a factor of α is scaled, the resulting process will be α times more volatile. This is useful in option pricing and risk management. Through this, GBM provides a framework for modeling the uncertainty and random fluctuations observed in assets over time.

The Black-Scholes Partial Differential Equation

In finance, the Black-Scholes equation is a partial differential equation (PDE). A partial differential equation is an equation that involves multiple independent variables, an unknown function that is dependent on those variables, and partial derivatives of the unknown function concerning those independent variables. For a European call or put option on an underlying asset with no dividends the equation is:

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} + rS \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} - rV = 0$$

In this equation, V is the price of the option as a function of stock price, which is S , and time which is t . The risk-free interest rate is r and σ is the volatility of the stock. This equation can be rewritten as:

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} = rV - rS \frac{\partial V}{\partial S}$$

The left-hand side of the equation consists of the "time-decay" term. It shows the change in the value (price) of the option (V) due to time increases, and the convexity of the option's value relative to the price of the stock (called theta). Gamma is the second spatial derivative of the option's value with respect to the asset price. The right-hand side of this equation is the riskless return from a long position in the derivative and a short position consisting of $\frac{\partial V}{\partial S}$ shares of the underlying asset.

In this equation, theta is typically negative, this is because the loss in value due to having less time for exercising the option is negative. On the other hand, Gamma is typically positive and so the gamma term reflects the gains in holding the option. This equation shows that over any infinitesimal time interval, the loss from theta and the gain from the gamma term should balance each other out. The result of this is a return at a riskless rate. Black and Scholes realized that the right-hand side is riskless, hence the equation states that the riskless return over any infinitesimal time interval can be expressed as the sum of theta and a term incorporating gamma.

The main reason for this is that hedging the options in a portfolio by buying and selling the underlying asset in just the right way will eliminate risk.

The solution to the Black-Scholes partially differential equation is called the Black-Scholes formula. Given the boundary conditions, it calculates the price of European put and call options. At maturity or expiration (T), the value of a European call (C) or put (P) option is given by, respectively:

$$C_{E,T} = \max(0, S_T - X)$$

$$P_{E,T} = \max(0, X - S_T)$$

Figure 1: A graph of the price of a European call option with respect to strike price and stock price, as calculated by the Black-Scholes equation

The boundary condition for the call option shows that the minimum value is 0 and the maximum value is the underlying asset price minus the exercise price (X). If the exercise price is higher than the asset price, then essentially the option is a put. Similarly, for the put option, the minimum is 0 and the maximum is the price of the underlying asset minus the exercise price. Black and Scholes found out that the functional form of the analytic solution to the Black-Scholes partial differential equation with the boundary conditions would be:

$$C = N(d_1)S - N(d_2)Xe^{-rt}$$

This formula is the main part of the Black-Scholes model and is what is the most useful in real life. This formula takes in two separate inputs, which are d_1 and d_2 , which will be mentioned later. The inputs that are going into this formula are:

S = the price of the security. The price of the security is the price of the underlying asset that the option is based on.

t = the time to maturity. This is essentially the lifespan of the option, or in how long the option will fully mature.

X = the exercise price. X (also in the boundary conditions) is the price at which the buyer of the option has the ability but not the obligation to exercise the option. It is what the buyer believes the asset will be worth at a specific time (the expiration date).

r = the risk-free interest rate. This represents the rate of return on an essentially "riskless" investment. Since this is not mathematically possible, it is a theoretical model. The closest approximation we have to the risk-free interest rate is by subtracting the current inflation rate from the yield of the US treasury bond for your current investment horizon. The US treasury bond is considered a riskless investment because the US has not defaulted on its debt.

σ = the standard deviation of the underlying asset. This is essentially a measure of volatility. This measure indicates how far the price of an asset varies from the mean. Intuitively, this means that the asset would be riskier, as the downside potential is higher, but the possibility for returns is also higher, as it can positively deviate from the mean. This is not in the actual formula but used in the inputs d_1 and d_2 .

The function $N()$ represents the cumulative distribution function for a normal distribution. This can be thought of as the probability that a random variable is less or equal to its input (in this case d_1 and d_2) for a normal distribution. Since it is about probability the value of $N()$ will always be between $0 \leq N() \leq 1$. It represents a standard normal distribution with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. The inputs for the equation that go into the function $N()$ are d_1 and d_2 . These are given by:

$$d_1 = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{S}{X}\right) + \left(r + \frac{\sigma^2}{2}\right)t}{\sigma\sqrt{t}}$$

$$d_2 = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{S}{X}\right) + \left(r - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}\right)t}{\sigma\sqrt{t}}$$

These two terms in the Black-Scholes formula can be informally thought of as the current price of the stock weighted by the probability that you will exercise the option subtracted by the discounted price of exercising the option weighted by the probability that you will exercise the option. d_1 is the probability that the value of the underlying asset is above the strike price, also called being "in the money". Additionally, it is the probability of how far in the money the option is in. It is the expected value multiplied by the probability that the stock price will be higher than the strike price. d_2 is the probability that the price of the underlying asset is greater than the strike price, called being "out of the money".

The first half of the equation is what you get. $N(d_1)S$ represents the probability of how much money the option will make multiplied by the stock price. This is the weighted stock price.

The second half of the equation is how much you have to pay for the option. The term e^{-rt} is

the discounting factor that gets multiplied by X (the strike price) to get a discounted value for the strike price today. If you multiply the discounted value of the strike price by the probability that the option is out of the money you will get the weighted exercise price.

So the overall formula, if you separate it into two halves, then it is much clearer to see how it shows the price of the option. The first term of the equation is the weighted stock price (taking in the probability), and the second term is the weighted strike price (discounted for today). And if you subtract the stock price and the strike price, you should be able to get the value for the option. And it also makes sense as the higher the asset price relative to the strike price, the more the asset would be worth.

In d_1 and d_2 , both use the ratio of the asset price to the exercise price ($\frac{S}{X}$), and the function is taking the natural log of it. That would mean that the larger the input into $N()$, the higher the probabilities given by the function are going to be, so it would have a higher chance that the option will be exercised.

Similarly, the higher the standard deviation (σ), the higher d_1 is going to go. This is because, even though σ is on the numerator and the denominator, it is squared in the numerator. That will lead to d_1 going up. On the other hand, for d_2 a higher σ is going to decrease d_2 . In the numerator, σ^2 is subtracted from the risk-free interest rate (r) leading to d_2 going down. So an increased σ will lead to the entire first term of the formula going up, and the entire second term of the formula will go down. So overall, if the amount you would get (the first half) goes up and the amount you would pay (the second half) goes down, then the entire value of the option will increase. So as a rule, when σ goes up, the value of the option will go up, and if σ goes down, the value of the option will go down.

For a put option, the formula is inverted. All the parts are the same but just in a different order. This is the Black-Scholes formula for a put option:

$$P = N(-d_2)Xe^{-rt} - N(-d_1)S$$

The inputs including d_1 and d_2 are the same, but the order of the terms makes all the difference. Similarly to the call formula, the first term in this formula (the second term in the other formula) is the strike price discounted back to today. It also accounts for the value of exercising the put option and selling the underlying asset at the strike price. Since $N(d_2)$ is the probability that the asset price is lower than the underlying asset, $N(-d_2)$ is the

probability that the option will be exercised at expiration. The second represents $N(-d_1)$ the probability that the option will not be exercised. Multiplying that by S calculating the expected value of the underlying asset at the time of expiration. If you subtract the first term from the second term, you are subtracting the present value of exercising the put option from the present value of the underlying asset. That should give you the value of the option.

Empirical Testing and Limitations

The empirical tests of the Black-Scholes model aim to examine how well the model's predictions match the actual market prices, and whether the model accurately captures the behavior of options over time. There have been a few empirical tests conducted to see the accuracy of the Black-Scholes model.

Comparison to observed option prices is one of the primary tests of the Black-Scholes model. This test involves comparing the model to the observed market prices of options. What the researchers did was that they analyzed a large number of options with a variety of strike prices and expiration dates. This was to see how accurately the model predicts real life. The result of this test was that the model provides a reasonable estimate for the options pricing. It also found that the model is most accurate for options that are close to expiration, deep in-the-money, or deep out-of-the-money. It is worse with options that are near-the-money. This leads to a systematic bias called a "volatility skew". This bias indicated that the model's assumption of constant volatility does not fully capture the market's pricing dynamics.

A big assumption for the Black-Scholes model is that the volatility remains the same. That doesn't take into account something called a volatility skew. This empirical test is to compare the implied volatilities from the Black-Scholes model to the observed implied volatilities taken from the market prices of options with the same strike prices, but different expiration dates. This test showed that in reality, the implied volatility is different than the ones predicted by the Black-Scholes model. The model tends to underestimate the implied volatilities for out-of-the-money options and overestimate it for the in-the-money options.

The sensitivity analysis test aims to assess the sensitivity of the Black-Scholes model to changes in its input parameters. By varying parameters like volatility, interest rates, and time to expiration, researchers can observe the corresponding changes in option pricing according to the model's predictions. This test had mixed results. While the model has a lot of sensitivity for expected sensitivities like changes in the price of the underlying asset, or time to expiration, there are instances where the model's predicted sensitives are different from the

market's sensitivities. An example is that the model may overestimate the sensitivities to changes in volatility or underestimate the sensitivity to changes in interest rates.

Another way to test the Black-Scholes model is by implementing option trading strategies based on its pricing formula and assessing its profitability. The researchers conducted trading strategies that exploited the model's assumptions such as delta-neutral or volatility trading strategies, and evaluated their performance over a period of time. This test also yielded mixed results. While certain strategies such as delta-neutral strategies have been successful, overall profitability remains challenging. If the strategies consistently generate options, that means that the model misprices options.

The Black-Scholes model generally provides reasonable assumptions for the pricing of options. When the option is close to expiration or deep in or out of the money, then it is the most accurate. When the option is near-the-money, then it is less accurate. This is when the volatility skew is more prominent. The model's assumption of constant volatility fails to capture the market dynamics related to volatility, resulting in an underestimation of out-of-the-money options and an overestimation of in-the-money options.

The model's sensitivity to input parameters generally aligns with the expectations. However, discrepancies between the model's predicted sensitivities and observed market sensitivities can occur, indicating potential limitations in capturing the full range of market dynamics. Additionally, during periods of high volatility, rapid price movements, or extreme events, the model may struggle to provide accurate pricing estimates due to its assumptions of constant volatility and normal distribution of returns.

The accuracy of the Black-Scholes model can also be influenced by market conditions and outliers. Factors like liquidity, transaction costs, and market closures, which are not accounted for in the model, can impact its pricing accuracy. Furthermore, the model's assumption of continuous trading and the absence of restrictions may not fully reflect the complexities and limitations of real market dynamics over extended periods.

Accurate parameter estimation is crucial for the model to be accurate. Volatility is particularly important for the validity of the model. Errors in estimating the parameters would lead to inaccurate outputs and results from the model.

Applications

As mentioned throughout the report, the Black-Scholes model is critical to the field of finance. Besides options, the Black-Scholes model also applies to other things in finance.

Option pricing is the most important and frequently used application of the Black-Scholes model. This is the main one discussed when addressing this model. Traders, investors, and other financial institutions rely on this model to calculate options pricing and make informed decisions regarding options trading and investment strategies.

The Black-Scholes model plays a crucial role in risk management. The model allows participants in the market to measure and manage their exposure to options and derivatives by quantifying the amount of risk they were taking. People can calculate this using the same Black-Scholes formula, but rearranging the equation. Traders and financial institutions can assess the sensitivity of option prices to changes in factors. These factors can include asset price, volatility, and time to expiration. This information allows parties to construct their hedging strategies and manage portfolio risk.

The Black-Scholes model's focus on volatility estimation and pricing has allowed parties to come up with their volatility trading strategies. Traders can use the model to identify mispriced options by calculating the implied volatility calculated by the model and the market's implied volatility. If there is a significant discrepancy, traders can exploit it by taking positions in options or volatility derivatives.

The model is also commonly used in the valuation of options and warrants in the context of mergers and acquisitions. When companies issue stock options or convertible assets, the model helps determine the value of these instruments. It helps in assessing the potential dilution effects of such securities on existing shareholders and provides a framework for negotiating the terms of such transactions.

The Black-Scholes formula is used to value employee stock options (ESOs). These ESOs are generally part of employees' compensation packages. Firms can use the Black-Scholes model to determine the "fair value" of the ESOs granted to employees. This helps to account for the cost of these options and complying with regulatory reporting requirements. Additionally, the model allows companies to estimate the impact of ESOs on their financial statements and make informed decisions about compensation plans.

Traders and investors can use the Black-Scholes model to develop and implement option trading strategies. The model's pricing formula provides insight into the relative value of different options and the potential profit or loss under various market scenarios. Traders and investors can construct strategies like covered calls, protective puts, and a multitude of

spreads based on the model's estimate of option prices and sensitivities to changes in underlying variables.

Beyond options, the Black-Scholes model has also been extended to value and price other types of financial derivatives, such as futures contracts and interest rate derivatives. By incorporating the model's principles and assumptions, analysts and financial institutions can estimate the fair value of these derivatives. This aids in trading, risk management, and investment decisions.

Discussion of the Strengths and Weaknesses

The main advantage of the Black-Scholes model, why it is so widely used is because of accuracy. It is one of the, if not the most accurate option pricing models which is available as compared to other option pricing models. The Black-Scholes model takes into account all of the factors that can affect the price of an option, including time to expiration, interest rates, volatility, and all the other important variables. The use of all these crucial variables leads to better and more accurate pricing of options contracts. This in turn gives this model an edge over others.

Another major benefit of the Black-Scholes model is the speed. It can price option contracts very quickly as it uses a mathematical formula to calculate the price of an option. This is one reason why it is such a popular choice for traders in the case of the stock market, the price changes within seconds, and traders need to make quick decisions about whether or not to buy or sell an option based on the price of the underlying asset (stocks or indexes in case of the stock market).

One more advantage of the Black-Scholes model is that its use is not limited. It can be used in the stock market, oil, and metals. It is flexible enough to be used in a variety of different situations. Thus, one can use this model to price options for about everything. That makes it a potent tool for traders who want to trade in a variety of assets.

Ignorance of other factors is one of the biggest disadvantages of the Black-Scholes model. This issue is that while calculating the theoretical value of the option contract, it only takes into account the price of the underlying asset, and ignores other potentially key factors. For example, it does not take into account factors such as dividends, interest rates, changes in volatility, external shocks, market regulatory actions, and so on. These are also the assumptions of the Black-Scholes model. This can in turn lead to some inaccuracies in the pricing of options.

The Black-Scholes model assumes that market participants can transact as much of the underlying asset as they want without changing the market's prices. During market crashes, liquidity often disappears, temporarily invalidating this premise.

The rest of the disadvantages of the Black-Scholes model are just related to the assumptions. The issue is that a lot of these assumptions are not necessarily accurate all of the time.

Conclusion

The Black-Scholes model utilizes the assumptions of Stochastic processes and Brownian motion to price options. It is heavily used in the world of finance and even though it is considered accurate, there could be other methods (such as machine learning, artificial intelligence, and quantum computing) that could price options with higher accuracy and efficiency than this model. Nevertheless, the Black-Scholes model is a prime example of how mathematics and finance can be combined with meaningful use.

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